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Circular SUsustainable FLOor coverings

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D7.1 Dissemination material

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Abbreviations

D	Deliverable
EC	European Commission
EU	European Union
WP	Work Package
KPI	Key Performance Indicator
TSG	Transition Support Group

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D7.1 - Dissemination Material

Introduction

This document consists of deliverable “D7.1 - Dissemination Material”. It accompanies the creation of dissemination materials and channels dedicated to the project: project website, social media channels, project flyer and poster.

In the following sections, the main structure, functioning and properties of the CISUFLO website will be presented. Then, there will be a section dedicated to the social media channels created for CISUFLO. To conclude, physical dissemination material (such as posters, flyers, leaflets, etc) will be reported and discussed in this document.

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1 CISUFLO Website

In this document a general overview of the CISUFLO website is provided. The website has been registered at the following address: www.cisuflo.eu. A landing page was created on June 9th, as the domain had been activated, shown in Figure 1. The landing page contained the links to the project LinkedIn and Twitter pages, the logos and relevant funding information, and the first press release. The website was published on July 31st.

Figure 1 - CISUFLO website landing page

ENCO is the responsible partner for its creation and maintenance with all partners contributing to verify it runs smoothly and correctly channels selected information to end-users.

ENCO, in accordance with the best-value for money principle, availed itself of the help of an external specialised graphical agency, E26, for the development of CISUFLO website. The logo and colors of the website aim to set a graphical identity for the project.

The website constitutes a fundamental dissemination channel of the project. It allows the general public to gather information and knowledge on the activities carried out within the scope of this action as well as it can reach the project's key stakeholders. It will be continuously updated as the project progresses.

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1.1 Website Structure

The website is structured in a total of eight main sections: 'Home'; 'Project'; 'Partners'; 'Pilots'; 'Transition Support Group'; 'News & Events'; 'Information & Downloads'; 'Contact Us'. Figure 2 provides a useful map of the website structure, including also the sub-sections where present.

Figure 2 - CISUFLO website structure

In the following sub-paragraphs each section will be introduced with a greater degree of detail.

1.1.1 Website Homepage

The CISUFLO website homepage presents itself as in Figure 3. The white header is fixed on top of the page. It showcases the project logo on the left and the main sections are listed on the right. Some sections have a drop-down menu that links visitors to the several website sub-sections.

Right below the header, there is a slider containing three pictures representing the main categories of materials on which CISUFLO focuses (textiles, wood and PVC). In Figure 3 it is possible to visualize the first of the three pictures coming in succession one after another.

A banner right under the slider states CISUFLO's mission: *"We are working on new technologies and products to improve materials' recovery and drive the flooring sector in Europe towards a circular model"*.

Figure 3 - CISUFLO website Homepage (1)

Running through the homepage, there is a section showcasing the UN’s SDGs to which CISUFLO will contribute (Figure 4).

Figure 4 - CISUFLO website Homepage (2)

The ‘Objectives’ section is reproduced also on the homepage of the website (Figure 5) to allow visitors to immediately grasp what is the ambition behind the project.

Figure 5 - CISUFLO website Homepage (3)

The website homepage finally contains a section with all the latest news published as in Figure 6.

Figure 6 - CISUFLO website Homepage (4)

The footer displayed in Figure 7 is present in all the sections of the website. It is made up of a form that invites visitors to subscribe to the project newsletter, and of a bar containing all the project details and funding information. This section is also connected with the project social media main pages, through the hyperlinks provided by the social media icons in the details bar.

Figure 7 - CISUFLO website Homepage (5)

1.1.2 Project page

The project section provides a summary of the context and scope of the action (Figure 8). The three sub-sections ('Objectives', 'Workplan' and 'Results') are available both via the sidebar menu and through the drop-down menu.

As anticipated above the 'Objectives' sub-section is resumed also in the homepage.

Figure 8 - CISUFLO website Project page

The 'Workplan' sub-section provides an overview of the main phases characterising the workflow of the project and a graphic representing a PERT chart, which shows the interrelations between the different workpackages, as visible in Figure 9. The 'Results' section will be filled with shareable outputs as soon as they have been produced.

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Workplan

The innovation activities will be implemented following a **three-phases workplan**. All phases will be continuously supported by Coordination (WP8) and Dissemination, Communication & Exploitation (WP7) activities.

Project
Objectives
Workplan
Results

Figure 9 - CISUFLO website Workplan page

1.1.3 Partners page

The section dedicated to CISUFLO partners displays the logos of all 19 partners. The partners' logos are organized by their role: Coordinator, Research Partners, Industry Partners and Associations. This order is supposed to facilitate visitors in the identification of specific categories of partners.

It is possible to obtain more information about each of the partners' organizations by clicking on their logos. Visitors will be redirected to their websites. Figure 10 shows this section of the website at a glance.

Research Partners:

Figure 10 - CISUFLO website Partners page

1.1.4 Pilots page

The ‘Pilots’ section contains a circular diagram (Figure 11) summarising the sequencing of the six pilots and their links with sectors other than flooring.

Figure 11 - CISUFLO website Pilots page

Following the chart, there are a series of summaries focused on each of the Pilots with a description of the main activities that will be carried out, the expected outcomes and an explicative image (Figure 12). A short summary is also dedicated to the ePRODIS system.

The Pilots sub-sections are accessible through both the side-bar and the drop-down menus.

PILOT 1

MANUFACTURING OF CIRCULAR FLOOR COVERINGS

Production of CISUFLO circular floor coverings (circular laminate flooring, circular vinyl flooring, circular textile flooring) with selection and processing of the materials according to the requirements for their post-use circularization:

- **Integration of tags** for their identification;
- **Design** that facilitates maintenance and removal;
- **Simulation** of product lifetime to ensure high quality;

Goals:

CLaminate: composed by >90% of recycled wood fibres;

CVinyl: composed by >90% of recycled PVC content;

CTextile: mono-material (PK) or easily separable product.

Figure 12 - CISUFLO website Pilots page (1)

1.1.5 Transition Support Group

The Transition Support Group section is meant to clarify the role and modality of participation of supporting entities.

TSG Members

Join the TSG

Transition support group (TSG)

This group participates to the project on a **voluntary basis** and contributes as **external stakeholders** to provide input and feedbacks.

Their contribution to the project is vital to ensure varying views from within the sector are heard as well to establish cross-sector synergies.

Thanks to the TSG members the impact of CISUFLO will be leveraged.

Transition support group (TSG)

TSG Members

Join the TSG

Figure 13 - CISUFLO website TSG page

The sub-section ‘TSG Members’ will be completed in accordance with the joining entities in the upcoming months, as the Transition Support Group will be definitively shaped.

The sub-section ‘Join the TSG’ invites potential stakeholders to apply to join the TSG. It contains a contact form to collect all the relevant information (Figure 14). Data are collected in accordance with the GDPR policy. Applicants have the chance to subscribe to the project newsletter.

Join the TSG

Is your company/institution involved in the flooring or in a linked sector? Are you interested in the CISUFLO project and willing to support it? You can apply to join the TSG board by filling out the form below.

To apply or ask information, fill the following form:

Subscribe Cisuflo Newsletter!

I declare to have read the privacy policy of this site and I authorize the processing of my personal data, pursuant to Articles 13, 14, 15 of Regulation EU 2016/679 - GDPR

Transition support group
(TSG)

TSG Members

Join the TSG

CONTACT US

Figure 14 - CISUFLO website Join the TSG page

1.1.6 News & Events

The ‘News & Events’ Section will contain all articles published on the website in the ‘News’ sub-section. The events organized within the context of this project or attended by the consortium will be available in the ‘Events’ sub-sections. Figure 15 provides an overview of the section at the time of writing.

Figure 15 - CISUFLO website News & Events page

1.1.7 Information & Downloads

This section is comprised of six sub-sections:

- **Public Deliverables**

Here it will be possible to consult and download all public deliverables of CISUFLO.

- **Newsletter**

The project newsletter issues will be made available in this section of the website.

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- **Communication Toolbox**

All the dissemination material (leaflet, posters, roll-ups) will be available to the general public at this section.

- **Circular Economy Link**

This section gathers links to key EU initiatives in the circularity and related fields.

- **Green Open Access Channel**

In this section visitors can find all the open access scientific publications that will be produced during the project.

- **OpenAire**

This section consists of an hyperlink to the project focus on the OpenAire platform (https://explore.openaire.eu/search/project?projectId=corda_h2020::5406bb4e0126a14bc7e16b8058604edf). OpenAire’s aim is to facilitate free and open access to European funded research.

Figure 16 - CISUFLO website Information & Downloads page

1.1.8 Contact Us

This section contains a contact form that interested visitors can fill in to request information. ENCO will collect and manage the incoming message inquiries. There are two tick boxes that guests are required to agree with: the privacy policy and the newsletter subscription, the latter being optional (Figure 17).

Figure 17 - CISUFLO website Contact Us page

1.2 Accessibility

The website has been built in a HTML5/PHP/CSS/JS structure. It has been built in WordPress®, a Content Management System that allows great leeway in editing and managing the website content. In this way the responsible partner, ENCO, can ensure that the website is always easy to update and that it runs smoothly throughout the project duration.

The website is accessible from different browsers. The interface is responsive, meaning that the CISUFLO website has been designed to offer a good navigation experience also to users who access it from mobile devices (i.e. smartphones or tablets). Figure 18, shows the Homepage appearance from a mobile device.

Figure 18 - CISUFLO website visualization from mobile device

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1.3 Access rights

ENCO, as WP7 and task 7.3 leader, is responsible for the creation, development and maintenance of the project website.

ENCO will entrust only a few profiles to edit and manage the content of the website.

1.4 Web traffic monitoring

The CISUFLO consortium aims to attract visitors and generate web traffic on the website. The desired target is to realize 35,000 website visits. To ensure being on the right track to meet this KPI the website's analytics will be continuously monitored.

Statistics provided by WordPress will be integrated with Google Analytics, a search engine optimization tool. Google analytics collects data on visitors and their behavior.

For instance, ENCO will be able to access information on:

- The geographical location, age group, language and country of visitors;
- The length of the navigation sessions on the CISUFLO website;
- Which sections of the website they visit;
- Whether they are new visitors or not, etc.

ENCO will store this data in a data repository in accordance with the GDPR 679/16.

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2 CISUFLO Social media channels

Social media channels are an effective tool to communicate the project and disseminate achievements and results to the wider public. The platforms chosen for CISUFLO are: Twitter, LinkedIn, Youtube and SlideShare.

The goal is to gather 4,500 followers, as a sum of the followers of the different accounts, and to share about 2,000 posts.

ENCO is responsible for setting up and managing the content of the social media pages. All partners will contribute to animate and engage on the project social networks account.

2.1 Twitter

ENCO set up a CISUFLO account on Twitter, available as @CISUFLO. Twitter distinguishes itself for the possibility of sharing only short-posts, meaning with only a limited number of digits.

Figure 19 shows the CISUFLO Twitter profile. The profile image is the project logo, while the banner acknowledges the funding agency.

Figure 19 - CISUFLO Twitter page

2.2 LinkedIn

ENCO created also a LinkedIn account for the project, available at this address: <https://www.linkedin.com/company/cisuflo/>. LinkedIn is a professional social network, particularly useful to create and nurture networks with stakeholders, enhance the project visibility and attract academics or peer community. Figure 20 shows the look of the CISUFLO profile on LinkedIn.

Figure 20 - CISUFLO LinkedIn page

LinkedIn also provides some interesting services such as analytics. Figure 21 provides a quick overview of the admin view of the CISUFLO LinkedIn account. ENCO will use this data to monitor the performance of the posts shared on this social media and gain useful insights for the communication strategy.

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Figure 21 - CISUFLO LinkedIn analytics

2.3 SlideShare

SlideShare is a community where it is possible to share professional content, such as presentations, infographics, documents, videos, etc. Figure 22 shows the CISUFLO account on this social platform.

Figure 22 – CISUFLO SlideShare Account

2.4 YouTube

YouTube is a video sharing platform where by creating a channel it is possible to share videos, comment and follow other channels.

The CISUFLO account on Youtube is displayed in Figure 23. The project logo is given prominence and funding information is included both in the banner and in the info box.

Figure 23 - CISUFLO Youtube channel

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3 CISUFLO physical dissemination material

The dissemination material will be distributed at physical events and conferences organized or attended by the consortium, and it will be made available online. As mentioned above, it will be possible to download the promotional toolkit in the 'Information & Downloads' section of CISUFLO website.

Once again web monitoring activities will help in determining whether the KPI of 2,500 visualization and 5,000 downloads is met.

This material will also be shared through our social network platform, described in section 2 of this document.

3.1.1 Graphical identity: project logo

The colours and graphical identity of the project are established through the project logo. Figure 24 shows the official logo chosen for the project.

Figure 24 - CISUFLO official logo

Before deciding in favour of the definitive version of the logo, different design options were considered.

<p>OPTION A</p>	
<p>OPTION B</p>	
<p>OPTION C</p>	
<p>OPTION D</p>	

Table 1 - CISUFLO logo version history

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It was decided in favor of a modified version of the first option because it is both simple and effective at the same time. The infinity symbol on the left evokes circularity, the different colour of the last three letters (FLO) draws attention to the acronym, and the full name stated below clarifies what CISUFLO is about.

3.1.2 Leaflet

Figure 25 and 26 show the leaflet that has been created for the CISUFLO project. The format is A5. The main page, right side of figure 25, shows the materials CISUFLO will treat and the logo, while the last page, on the left in figure 25, includes all the contacts, funding information and the logos of the consortium.

Figure 25 - CISUFLO leaflet

The inside of the leaflet is represented in Figure 26. It summarises the context, goal and expected results of the project on the left page. On the right page it shows the graphics related to the pilots and a focus on the ePRODIS system.

The leaflet will be made available both on the website for online visualization and download, and it will be handed out during events in a printed format.

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Figure 26 - CISUFLO leaflet (1)

3.1.3 Poster

The poster created for the project is displayed in Figure 27. On the top it shows CISUFLO materials and the logo. It summarizes the challenge and the goal of the project. In the centre there is the graphic related to the 6 pilots. The footer contains all funding information, contacts and the logos of the partners of the consortium.

It is a 70x100 cm sized poster that will be made available online and displayed during conferences or events.

THE PROBLEM: THE FLOORING SECTOR IS STILL FAR FROM BEING SUSTAINABLE. ONLY A VERY **SMALL PORTION** OF THE FLOORING WASTE IS **RECYCLED** ACCORDING TO RECENT ESTIMATES.

THE SOLUTION: **CISUFLO** AIMS TO CHANGE THIS STATUS QUO BY DELIVERING NEW CIRCULAR PRODUCTS AND IMPROVE MATERIAL RECOVERY IN THE EU FLOORING SECTOR, TAKING INTO ACCOUNT BOTH TECHNICAL FEASIBILITY AND SOCIO-ECONOMIC FACTORS.

Figure 27 - CISUFLO poster

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Conclusions

This document constitutes 'D7.1 – Dissemination Material'. The first section provides an overview of the website created for the CISUFLO project by ENCO, with the help of an external specialised agency E26.

In the second section there is a summary of the social media platforms that CISUFLO will engage on.

Finally the third and last section showcases the promotional material created at the time of writing to communicate and disseminate the project.

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I. Annex

Privacy Policy

is regulated by Italian law and in particular by Legislative Decree no. 196 of 30 June 2003 (Personal data protection code, the “Code”), as well as the European Regulation 2016/679 “GDPR” (the “Regulation”) in force since 25th May 2018.

1. PERSONAL DATA CONTROLLER

Enco Srl with registered office 80122 Naples – Via Michelangelo Schipa 115 (hereinafter Enco) is the data controller for the data processing related (“Controller”) to the Sites, including therein browsing data, as well as all the data connected and related to online sales.

For any questions on this Privacy Policy, to have a whole list of the appointed Data Processors and to send a request for exercising the data subject’s rights, you can contact the Data Controller by writing to the following email address info@cisuflo.eu or send a request to the address of the registered office noted above.

2. PERSONAL DATA COLLECTED

a) Sign up for the newsletter

By subscribing to the newsletter, the user provides the following personal data: name, surname, email. These data are necessary, therefore, in the absence of such data, it will not be possible to register for the newsletter or to create an account.

b) Assistance / request for information

To obtain a support service or to request information, the User can send a request to the email address info@cisuflo.eu or to the other email addresses indicated on the Website, or use one of the electronic forms present in the Website, and must provide the following personal data: name, surname, mail, message. These data are necessary: failure to provide such data could prevent Enco from providing the requested assistance.

c) Browsing data

During the browsing of the Site by the user, the information systems and software procedures relied upon to operate these Sites acquire personal data as part of their standard functioning, the transmission of such data is an inherent feature of Internet communication protocols.

This data category includes the IP addresses and/or the domain names of the computers and terminal equipment used by any user, the URI/URL (Uniform Resource Identifier/Locator) addresses of the requested resources, the time of such requests, the method used for submitting a given request to the server, returned file size, a numerical code relating to server response status (successfully performed, error, etc.), and other parameters related to the user’s operating system and computer environment.

d) Cookies

Regarding the use of cookies, please refer to the Cookie Policy published on the Website.

If the user provides personal data of third parties (for example, family members, other customers or potential customers), the user should make sure that such third parties are informed and authorized the use of their data as described in this Privacy Policy. The user will remain the only responsible for the communication of information and data relating to third parties without the latter having given their consent or for their possible incorrect use or against the law.

3. PURPOSE OF THE PROCESSING, LEGAL BASIS AND DATA STORAGE PERIOD

3.1 Newsletter subscription and request for information via web form

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The personal data provided by the user or collected when the user subscribes to the newsletter on the Website or requests information via web form, will be used:

- to provide the services requested (for example, assist and manage any complaints and respond to a request or contact request that may be submitted by the user, also through customer service);
- to manage newsletter subscription

Personal data must be provided for the aforementioned purposes and the refusal would prevent to complete the request.

The processing of data for the afore mentioned purposes is carried out to follow up the request to receive newsletters and manage the request of information / assistance.

The personal data processed for newsletter subscription will be kept until the user requests cancellation from the newsletter.

The personal data processed for the assistance / request for information will be kept for the time necessary to manage the request, and then they will be eliminated

Without prejudice to the foregoing, the user's personal data will be kept only for any legal and regulatory obligations (such as, for example, accounting and tax obligations).

3.2 Use of web services

The browsing data, which are acquired by the Controller during the browsing of the Website by the Customer, are necessary for the use of web-based services and are also processed in order to:

- extract statistical information on service usage (most visited pages, visitors by time/date, geographical areas of origin, etc.);
- check functioning of the services.

Browsing data are kept for no longer than seven days and are erased immediately after being aggregated (except where judicial authorities need such data for establishing the commission of criminal offences).

3.3 Marketing

Personal data collected on the Website will be used, after obtaining consent, to offer promotions and send newsletters, other communications, surveys and researches, market analysis, promotions and other initiatives for customers ("marketing"). The Controller may use traditional (postal mail and telephone) and/or digital and automated (e-mail, SMS) contact means.

The use of data for marketing purposes is optional and free, being based on the consent that the user can choose to lend. The user can revoke his consent at any time. In any case, the refusal to provide personal data for marketing purposes does not prevent the user from using the services of the Sites or making purchases, but the same will not be informed of marketing initiatives promoted by the Controller.

Personal data processed for marketing purposes will be kept, in accordance with the provisions of the Italian data protection authority's (hereinafter the Garante), for a period not exceeding 24 months, unless the user renews his consent and except for further measures issued by the Garante.

Passed the retention period indicated above, personal data will be permanently deleted or anonymised. Without prejudice to the foregoing, the user's personal data will be kept only for any legal and regulatory obligations (such as, for example, accounting and tax obligations).

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4. COMMUNICATION OF PERSONAL DATA

The personal data of the user will be processed by authorised persons of the Controller and, if appointed, the Processor.

Personal data may also be processed by third parties who perform, for example, services for sending communications via e-mail or SMS, computer system maintenance services, computer assistance services and Content management application.

The above-mentioned persons will only process the personal data necessary for the performance of the related services and will not be authorized to process them for different purposes.

The user's personal data may also be communicated to other persons, such as law enforcement agencies, administrative or judicial authorities and public administrations for the fulfillment of legal obligations, regulations or community provisions.

5. PROTECTION OF THE PRIVACY OF MINOR

The processing of personal data of the minor is lawful where the child is at least 16 years old. If the child is under the age of 16, such treatment is lawful only if the consent is given or authorized by the holder of parental responsibility.

The Data Controller will, in any reasonable way and in consideration of the available technologies, make sure that the consent is given or authorized by the holder of parental responsibility on the child.

If the Data Controller or the Processor come to know that a minor's data have been collected, they will immediately cancel them.

In the event that the user is not of the required age, please do not register or proceed with the online purchase and ask an adult (or their parents or legal guardian) to perform the necessary procedures.

6. METHOD OF PROCESSING

The personal data collected through the Sites is processed mainly using computerized and telematic methods and tools, adopting the necessary security measures in order to minimize the risk of destruction or loss, even accidental, of the data, unauthorized access or of treatment not allowed or not in accordance with the collection purposes indicated in this statement. However, these measures, due to the nature of the online transmission medium, cannot limit and exclude absolutely any risk of unauthorized access or data loss. To this end, the user is advised to: periodically check that the computer is equipped with appropriate software devices for the protection of data transmission in the network, both incoming and outgoing (as updated antivirus systems); verify that the internet service provider has taken appropriate measures for the security of data transmission over the network (such as, for example, firewalls and antispam filters). In the event that the Controller believes that the security of the personal data of the user in his possession or under his control has been or may have been compromised, the same will inform the user of the incident according to the procedures established by the law in force, using the methods prescribed by it (providing his/her email address to the Controller, the user consents to receive such communications in electronic format through this email address).

7. TRANSFERS TO THIRD COUNTRIES OR INTERNATIONAL ORGANIZATIONS

Should the Controller transfer personal data to third countries or international organizations, in order to pursue the purposes set out in this Privacy Policy, the Controller will take measures to ensure that such communications are carried out in accordance with European data protection standards (for example, use of standard contractual clauses or Privacy Shield).

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8. USER RIGHTS

To exercise the rights indicated below, the user can send a request by contacting the Controller and by sending an email to info@cisuflo.eu or a letter by postal mail to the address of the Controller. When contacting the Controller, the user must include his name, email address, postal address and/or telephone number(s) to be sure that the Controller can correctly handle his/her request.

8.1 Right of access

The user shall have the right to obtain confirmation as to whether or not personal data concerning him or her are being processed, and, where that is the case, access to the personal data and the following information: the purposes of the processing; the categories of personal data; the recipients or categories of recipient; where possible, the envisaged period for which the personal data will be stored, or, if not possible, the criteria used to determine that period; the existence of the right to request from the controller rectification or erasure of personal data or restriction of processing of personal data concerning the data subject or to object to such processing; the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority; where the personal data are not collected from the user, any available information as to their source; the existence of automated decision-making, including profiling, and, at least in those cases, meaningful information about the logic involved, as well as the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the user; Where personal data are transferred to a third country or to an international organisation, the user shall have the right to be informed of the appropriate safeguards relating to the transfer.

The user has the right to obtain a copy of the personal data undergoing processing.

8.2 Right of rectification

The user shall have the right to obtain from the Controller without undue delay the rectification of inaccurate personal data concerning him or her. Taking into account the purposes of the processing, the user shall have the right to have incomplete personal data completed, including by means of providing a supplementary statement.

8.3 Right to erasure

The user shall have the right to obtain from the controller the erasure of personal data concerning him or her without undue delay and the controller shall have the obligation to erase personal data without undue delay where one of the following grounds applies:

- the personal data are no longer necessary in relation to the purposes for which they were collected or otherwise processed;
- the user withdraws consent on which the processing is based, with an email or postal communication;
- the user objects to the processing and there are no overriding legitimate grounds for the processing, or the user objects to the processing for direct marketing purposes, which includes profiling;
- the personal data have been unlawfully processed;
- the personal data have to be erased for compliance with a legal obligation in Union or Member State law to which the Controller is subject;
- the personal data have been collected in relation to the offer of information society services directly to a child.

8.4 Right of restriction

D7.1 - Dissemination Material

The user shall have the right to obtain from the controller restriction of processing where one of the following applies:

- a) the accuracy of the personal data is contested by the user, for a period enabling the controller to verify the accuracy of the personal data;
- b) the processing is unlawful and the user opposes the erasure of the personal data and requests the restriction of their use instead;
- c) the Controller no longer needs the personal data for the purposes of the processing, but they are required by the user for the establishment, exercise or defence of legal claims;
- d) the user has objected to processing pursuant to Article 21(1) pending the verification whether the legitimate grounds of the Controller override those of the data subject.

8.5 Right to data portability

The user shall have the right to receive the personal data concerning him/her, which he/she has provided to a controller, in a structured, commonly used and machine-readable format and have the right to transmit those data to another controller without hindrance from the controller to which the personal data have been provided, where:

- a) the processing is based on consent pursuant to point (a) of Article 6(1) or point (a) of Article 9 (2) of Regulation or on a contract pursuant to point (b) of Article 6(1) of Regulation;
- b) the processing is carried out by automated means.

In exercising his/her right to data portability pursuant to paragraph 1, the user shall have the right to have the personal data transmitted directly from one controller to another, where technically feasible.

8.6 Right to object

The user shall have the right to object, on grounds relating to his/her particular situation, at any time to processing of personal data concerning him/her which is based on point (e) or (f) of Article 6(1), including profiling based on those provisions.

8.7 Further rights

The user shall have the right not to be subjected to a decision based only on automated processing, including profiling, which produces legal effects that affect him/her or that significantly affects his person.

The user shall have the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority (in Italy, the Italian data protection authority's, Garante).

9. UPDATE OF PERSONAL DATA

The user is invited to check and update their personal data on a regular basis. To this end, in case of changes, the user is invited to write to the email address info@cisuflo.eu or to directly modify the data online using the settings of the user account on the Website, where registered.

10. UPDATES OF THIS INFORMATION – COMMUNICATIONS

The Controller reserves the right to modify, add or delete parts of this Privacy Policy at any time by publishing the revised version on this page of the Website and updating the date of the “last modification” indicated below.

It is the responsibility of the user to read, from time to time, the Information to be aware of any changes made. In some cases, the Controller may provide further communications regarding significant changes to this Information by posting a notice on the home page of this Website or, in the case of registered users, by sending a notification email or by posting a notice on their account page.